

National and industry culture combined: Preferred leader profile in the retail industry

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Abstract: Management in retail industry is market by diverse set of challenges which effect business performance. However, leadership may play a pivotal role for resolving these issues. Nevertheless, despite the primary evidence pointing at the integral role of leadership and the variety of its effects in retail, the contextualized view of leadership in this industry remains equivocal. Therefore, the following study aimed to contribute to addressing this gap by development of a preferred managerial leader's behavioral prototype in the retail industry, which serves as bases for leadership effectiveness. This quantitative research, based on a sample of 211 employees in the retail industry in Lithuania, presents contextualized insights into explicit leader prototypes held by the followers, demonstrated through their perceptions of preferred leader behavior. The study also emphasizes the role of industrial and national cultural values in the construction of a preferred managerial leader's behavioral prototype. This study unveiled a set of contextualized insights into followercentric leader profiles that both contribute to the cross-industrial and cross-cultural strand of research and serve as direct implications for practitioners.

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1. Introduction

The fast-paced retail industry has also been regarded as a labor intensive industry (Zopiatis, Constanti, & Theocharous, 2014). Relatedly, this industry is marked by high employee turnover, posing an additional set of challenges for the top-level management to retain sales force (Deeter-Schmelz, Goebel, & Kennedy, 2008), especially in the light of a widespread consensus that retailers, along with other types of companies in the service industry, rely on frontline employees for delivering services, developing customer relationships, and success of business performance (Babakus, Yavas, Karatepe, & Avci, 2003; Ifie, 2014; Korschun, Bhattacharya & Swain, 2014). In turn, previous studies have demonstrated that high frontline employee turnover can affect customer service quality (Alexandrov, Babakus, & Yavas, 2007). Extant findings on leadership in the retail industry suggest that leadership behavior can affect employee attitudes and behavior (e.g. Shim, Lusch, & O'Brien, 2002). Thus, leadership may play a pivotal role for both harnessing employee turnover, and fostering individual-related outcomes, including, for example, employee self-efficacy, hope, positive affect and creativity (Rego, Sousa, Marques, & Cunha, 2012) that are critical in the retail industry, including the impact of emotions on turnover intentions (Cho, Rutherford, Friend, Hamwi, Park, 2017). Nevertheless, despite the primary evidence pointing at the integral role of leadership and the variety of its

effects in retail (Runyan & Droge, 2008), the contextualized view of leadership in this industry remains equivocal (Lindblom, Kajalo, & Mitronen, 2016).

In response to the aforementioned gaps, this study was conducted with a purpose to construct a preferred managerial leader's behavioral profile in the retail industry. Taking into account the complicated nature of implicit and explicit leadership schemas, we relied on explicit manifestations of leadership, namely, the behavior of a preferred managerial leader (Littrell, 2010, 2013). We respectively aligned our study with a follower-centric perspective, simultaneously contributing to filling in the existing gap, related to abundant leader-centric research (Littrell, 2010). In line with Yukl (2013) we also gave particular attention to cultural nuances that may affect follower expectations and perceptions concerning leader behavior and its effectiveness. In this study, we combine both the national and industrial culture perspectives as both have influence on the culture shared among the members of an organization (House, Hanges, Javidan, Dorfman, & Gupta, 2004).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. First, theoretical grounding for deriving an industry- and culture-specific behavioral prototype of a leader is provided. Then, we outline the methodology for the empirical investigation and discuss the results, comparing them with the insights in other cultures. Finally, we provide a number of implications for researchers and practitioners.

2. Theoretical background

Awareness about the expectations in a particular context, or applied settings, can be instrumental for leadership development (Epitropaki, Sy, Martin, Tram-Quon, & Topakas, 2013). In turn, a contextualized view of leadership in the retail industry calls for taking into account specificities in both the industry and the national culture. On an industry level, currently available manifold findings underscore the impacts of leadership, albeit with a non-unified portrait of preferred leadership behaviors. For example, stressors stemming from supervisors are related with turnover intentions among frontline employees (Kao, Cheng, Kuo, & Huang, 2014), while supervisors who exhibit servant and ethical leadership behavior can produce a mitigating effect on the negative perceptions towards the organizational processes, experienced by the subordinates, as, for example, demonstrated in the study on sales, by Jaramillo, Grisaffe, Chonko, & Roberts (2009). Similarly, transformational leadership practices can form an important element for store retail manager strategies aimed at reducing employee turnover (Love, 2019). However, while development and training in transformational leadership are linked with positive outcomes for retail managers (Keevy & Perumal, 2014), both transactional and transformational leadership profiles are considered to be characterizing successful store managers (Duckett & Macfarlane, 2003). Similarly, MacKenzie, Podsakoff, and Rich (2001) have pointed at the combination of transformational and transactional leadership practices for effective in-role sales performance. It may also have double-sided effects, such as supporting the sales planning behaviors, but suppressing the selling orientation of the store managers (Arnold, Palmatier, Grewal, & Sharma, 2009).

Additionally, other findings signal more nuanced, follower-dependent perceptions of leaders. Sales managers, who enact the roles of sales leaders, should promote confidence, trust, and open communication, as perceived by salespersons (Deeter-Schmelz, Goebel, & Kennedy, 2008). Nevertheless, Kim and Shim (2003) report that differences in perception

regarding the leader's role may exist depending on gender. Therefore, understanding the differences in perceptions among followers can become even more critical, given the intensity of labor and employee turnover.

As the wider literature on organizational leadership demonstrates, effective and ineffective leadership behaviors, as perceived by the followers or subordinates, are context-dependent, especially so across national cultures (e.g. Javidan, Dorfman, Du Luque, & House, 2006; Casimir, Waldman, Bartram, & Yang, 2006; Vogel et al., 2015). Just as culture both glues specific groups of individuals and differentiates them from others (Hofstede, Hofstede, & Minkov, 2005), specific attitudes and behavior partly emanate from culture (Yukl, 2013). Likewise, followers across cultures demonstrate a variety of specific, culturally linked expectations, which are required to be met by their leaders (Littrell, 2010). Therefore, national culture, together with the professional culture within the industry, becomes an inseparable layer for analysis of the preferred leader behavior prototypes, driven by expectations of their followers.

Finally, expectations for leaders can be derived from implicit leadership theories (or schemas) held by the followers, which reflect the prototypes or profiles of leader traits and abilities (Lord and Maher, 1991). As House et al. (2004) connote, the idealized leader's behavioral prototype is a reflection of the follower's expectations, closely linked with the anticipated change and future outcomes, rather than the present states. Therefore, the methodology of this study, presented further, is grounded in constructing a leader behavioral profile through experientially formed perceptions of the followers, while involving both industrial and national cultural aspects.

3. Methodology

In an attempt to construct a profile of a preferred, rather than existing leadership behavior, we employed LBDQ-XII (Stogdill, 1963) as a viable instrument (Rodriguez, 2012). Leader Behavior Description Questionnaire XII is the most widely used instrument in leadership field (Northouse, 2013), which can effectively describe preferred leader behavior in particular cultures. Furthermore, as extensively elaborated in Warner-Soderholm, Minelgaite and Littrell (2019), the reliability and validity of the LBDQXII has been well researched during its development and well-documented in the literature. We also acknowledged and aimed to mitigate the possible influence of the implicit leader profile that a researcher may hold (Goethals, Sorenson & Burns, 2004). LBDQ-XII hence enabled us to measure 12 factors describing preferred leader behavior: Representation, Demand reconciliation, Tolerance of uncertainty, Persuasiveness, Initiation of structure, Tolerance of freedom, Role assumption, Consideration, Production emphasis, Predictive accuracy, Integration, and Superior orientation. A 5-point Likert-type scale was used for responses concerning preferred managerial leader's behavior (where 1 = "Never", and 5 = "Always"). In order to tease out the cultural dimensions apparent in the retail industry in Lithuania, we selected Values Survey Module (VSM08) that captures Power distance (PDI), Uncertainty avoidance index (UAI), Individualism vs. collectivism (IDV), Masculinity vs. femininity (MAS), Long-term orientation (LTO), Indulgence vs. restraint (IVR), Monumentalism vs. self-effacement (MON) (Hofstede et al., 2008). The internal reliability coefficient for the scores was 0.912.

A convenience sample (n=211) of retail employees of the members of the Association of Lithuanian Trade Enterprises participated in the study. Of 211 respondents, 84% were

female and 16% male. The majority of participants held middle-management (45%) or specialist (29%) positions, while 13% held top-management positions, 9% were employed as administrative personnel, and 3% were employed as operatives. All participants predominantly had a degree in higher education: 28% had college education completed, while 28% held a bachelor's and 22% held a master's degree.

4. Discussion

All respondents predominantly indicated no preference for gender in preferred leader profile (91.94%). As it can be observed in Figure 1, participants of the study gave relatively high scores to all factors (9 factors were rated above "4"), with Integration (4.62), Representation (4.54), and Initiation of structure (4.42) emerging as the most prominent factors. Tolerance of uncertainty (3.50), Tolerance of freedom (3.88), and Production emphasis (3.90) were considered as the least important. These perceptions are unified between male and female followers.

FIGURE 1. LBDQ-XII SCORES

In this vein, a prototype of a preferred managerial leader portrays an individual who undertakes and enacts the role of a leader, primarily exhibits an integrative approach to followers, including the emphasis on the team, conflict resolution, and team representation. A high followers' preference for Initiation of structure suggests that they expect the leader to define and support clear rules, norms, and tasks. Such a leader will be productively demanding and will delineate the degrees of freedom, thus keeping up with efficiency, however, he or she will not put the well-being of the followers at stake in order to achieve the goals.

An additional ANOVA analysis (Table 1) revealed that follower's education may affect the perceptions concerning the preferred managerial leader's behavioral profile. The follower's degree of education is related to preferences in terms of Demand reconciliation, Initiation of structure, Tolerance of freedom, and Production emphasis. In sum, higher education is

associated with increased expectations for Demand reconciliation and Tolerance of freedom. On the lower end of the spectrum, less educated followers exhibit greater preference for Initiation of structure and Production emphasis exercised by the managerial leader. Interestingly, employees who hold high-level positions in a company also value Initiation of structure and Production emphasis. Age-specific level of analysis similarly revealed that greater follower's age is also significantly related with prioritization of Initiation of structure and Production emphasis.

TABLE 1. CORRELATIONS FOR EDUCATION AND LEVEL OF POSITION (KRUSKAL-WALLIS)-XII

EDUCATION	LBDQ FACTORS			
	DEMAND RECONCILIATION	INITIATION OF STRUCTURE	TOLERANCE OF FREEDOM	PRODUCTION EMPHASIS
<i>PROFESSIONAL/COLLEGE DEGREE</i>				
r	4.13 (.64)**	4.51 (.38)**	3.82 (.46)*	3.97 (.38)*
Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.006	.046	.026
N	78	78	78	78
<i>BACHELOR'S DEGREE</i>				
r	4.36 (.49)**	4.44 (.34)**	3.83 (.41)*	3.93 (.31)*
Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.006	.046	.026
N	64	64	64	64
<i>MASTER'S DEGREE</i>				
r	4.47 (.50)**	4.30 (.42)**	3.99 (.46)*	3.81 (.39)*
Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.006	.046	.026
N	69	69	69	69

Note: ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$.

FIGURE 2. VSM08 SCORES

Further cultural value analysis depicted that followers in the retail industry in Lithuania relatively emphasize Power distance index and Monumentalism in contrast to other dimensions, suggesting the expectations regarding clear instructions from their managerial leaders, alongside respect for hierarchy, status, and privilege. Uncertainty avoidance index was rated relatively low, signifying the tolerance of ambiguity, balanced out by respect for

rules, relatively low loyalty to the employer and general presence of satisfaction, as shown in Figure 2.

Further correlational analysis documents several statistically significant associations between cultural dimensions and LBDQ-XII factors attributed to the preferred managerial leader prototype held by the followers in the retail industry (Table 2).

TABLE 2. CORRELATIONS FOR CULTURAL (VSM08) AND LBDQ-XII DIMENSIONS

LBDQ-XII FACTOR	CULTURAL DIMENSION	r	p
Tolerance of uncertainty	Uncertainty avoidance	-.156*	.023
	Long-term orientation	-.141*	.041
	Indulgence vs. restraint	.151*	.028
Persuasiveness	Indulgence vs. restraint	-.252**	<.001
Initiation of structure	Individualism vs. collectivism	-.139*	.043
	Masculinity vs. femininity	-.158*	.022
	Indulgence vs. restraint	-.172	.012
Tolerance of freedom	Individualism vs. collectivism	.145*	.035
	Masculinity vs. femininity	-.239**	<.001
	Monumentalism	.148*	.031
Consideration	Masculinity vs. femininity	-.150*	.029
Production emphasis	Indulgence vs. restraint	-.151*	.029
Predictive accuracy	Indulgence vs. restraint	-.230**	.001
Integration	Power distance	-.158*	.022
	Masculinity vs. femininity	-.195**	.004
Superior orientation	Indulgence vs. restraint	-.175*	.011

Note: ** p < .01; * p < .05.

As portrayed in Table 2, the follower's Uncertainty avoidance and Long-term orientation negatively correlate with managerial leader's Tolerance of uncertainty. Follower's Indulgence vs. restraint positively correlates with leader's Tolerance of uncertainty, but negatively correlates with follower's Persuasiveness, Initiation of structure, Production emphasis, Predictive accuracy, and Superior orientation. Follower's Individualism vs. collectivism negatively correlates with leader's initiation of structure and positively correlates with leader's Tolerance of freedom. Follower's Masculinity vs. femininity negatively correlates with leader's Initiation of structure, Tolerance of freedom, Consideration, and Integration. Follower's acknowledgement of Monumentalism as a value positively correlates with leader's Tolerance of freedom. Follower's appreciation of Power distance is positively associated with leader's Integration. In sum, follower's positioning in terms of cultural values is specifically evident through Indulgence vs. restraint dimension that has the largest number of associations with preferred leader behavioral characteristics.

5. Limitations of research

Our study is subject to a number of limitations that at the same time pertain to the new avenues for the further empirical studies. Firstly, our study serves as a primary investigation which is based on a correlational design and warrants future studies to derive and investigate hypothesized causalities and employ a variety of methodological approaches. For example, further studies may examine whether the relatively high scores

on the Power-distance index (PDI), observed within the retail industry precede or grow out of the followers' expectations for the leaders to reduce uncertainty. Secondly, the study is restrained to cross-sectional design and a single point in time. Studies based on a longitudinal approach may set the base for disclosing the changes in perceptions as they unfold along with, for example, different individual-related affective states or leader-follower relationship dynamics and development over time. Relatedly, analysis of and between the leader and follower behavioral prototypes held by followers and leaders respectively, could significantly augment our understanding of their interaction.

6. Conclusion

From a cultural perspective, Uncertainty avoidance marks an equivocal interplay between national culture, industry culture, and follower perceptions. On a national level, Lithuania scores moderately to high on the Uncertainty avoidance index, with a score of 65 (Huettinger, 2008; Hofstede Insights, 2019), reflecting low Tolerance to risk, and expectations towards superiors to have superior knowledge, experience, and answers under uncertain circumstances. On an industry-level, followers in the retail industry report relatively low scores on the Uncertainty avoidance index, with an average of -26, suggesting that employees adhere to rules and norms, yet, are tolerant of uncertainty and ambiguity. In line with the general findings on the labor-intensive retail industry, where employee turnover rates are high, these results indicate potentially low employee loyalty to the employer. While the collected data does not enable one to infer a conclusion whether such a cultural standing is specifically an antecedent or a consequence of the industrial context, it is likely that both are intertwined. Nevertheless, regardless the divergence from the findings on a level of the national culture, the followers in the retail industry are still anticipating their leaders to be less tolerant of uncertainty, as well as freedom, and thus likely provide them with clear answers, rules, and norms, supplemented with strong Initiation of structure.

These insights are complemented with an industry-specific insight that diverges from the general national outlook. While Huettinger (2008) and Hofstede et al. (2010) position Lithuania among the countries that moderately score on Power-distance index (PDI), the findings of the present study in the retail industry hint at the rather high scores on PDI. Again, current analysis does not enable us to infer conclusions whether these results on PDI are a potential precursor or subsequently stem from the expectation for the leaders to reduce uncertainty and clear the path for the followers by, for example, initiating structure. However, they pinpoint the contextual differences which exist despite the national culture.

A cross-cultural comparison of the preferred, or desirable, leader profile in the retail industry in Lithuania with findings from China, Romania, Germany, and United Kingdom (Littrell, 2002), highlights the presence of cultural differences in the perceptions of followers. Differently from these cultures, the followers in Lithuania prioritize Initiation of structure, Consideration, and Integration. On the other hand, the Tolerance of risk and freedom, along with Persuasiveness and Emphasis on production, are considered to be less important. Interestingly, out of all cultures under consideration, leader profile in this industry in Lithuania most closely matches the prototype in China. All factors being valued rather similarly, the differences are observed with regard to Role assumption, which is rated higher in Lithuania, and Emphasis on production that is more prioritized in China. On a broader cultural spectrum, this finding is in line with results by Hofstede et al. (2010) on relatively low scores on Indulgence versus restraint (IVR) in both cultures.

While the scores on IVR are relatively moderate, they were most highly related with behavioral dimensions.

By investigating follower perceptions, our study unveiled a set of contextualized insights into follower-centric leader profiles that both contribute to the cross-industrial and cross-cultural strand of research and serve as direct implications for practitioners. The study also emphasizes the role of industrial and national cultural values in the construction of a preferred managerial leader's behavioral profile. The study results point to Representation, Demand reconciliation, Persuasiveness, Initiation of structure, and Integration as the key behavior manifestations that followers in the retail industry are anticipating from their leaders. On the contrary, such dimensions as Tolerance of Uncertainty and Tolerance of freedom are perceived as potentially having a negative influence on the effectiveness of leadership behavior. Followers are likely to adhere to the script, while being tolerant of uncertainty and ambiguity, and attributing uncertainty and ambiguity to the capabilities of their leaders. Statistically significant, although weak, correlations between cultural dimensions and preferred leadership behavior have been detected. The obtained findings illustrate how relatively prominent Power distance and Monumentalism, as well as low Uncertainty avoidance is in a given industry and that national culture can possibly be related with the differences in follower perceptions of managerial leadership behavior. These results, albeit limited, reinforce the importance of embedding cultural aspects into leadership behavior analysis.

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